

THIRD UNITED NATIONS OCEAN CONFERENCE

RECOMMENDATIONS TO HEADS OF STATE AND GOVERNMENT

FROM THE INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE OF THE ONE OCEAN SCIENCE CONGRESS

.EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Ocean is a global common good, essential to sustaining life and prosperity on Earth through its vast biodiversity and critical ecosystem services. Scientists aim at delivering relevant, timely, and evidence-based guidance to decision-makers as they address global ocean challenges, including the impacts of, and solutions to climate change, biodiversity loss, and environmental degradation. At this critical juncture for our planet, there is a need to establish and nurture close interactions between scientists and decision-makers, across diverse value systems, including Indigenous and local knowledge, to advocate for science-based policies that promote long-term ocean sustainability, engage the public, foster inclusiveness, and stimulate innovation through interdisciplinary research.

Grounded in scientific evidence, we advance 10 thematic recommendations aligned with the Ocean Action Panels¹ to shape discussions at the 2025 United Nations Ocean Conference (Table 1). These recommendations are outlined below, with specific actions detailed in the following sections:

1. Inspire responsibility and respect for the ocean, integrating across knowledge systems.
2. Enable effective, equitable and environmentally safe ocean-based approaches to achieve the mitigation and adaptation goals of the Paris Agreement.
3. Effectively protect and restore marine and coastal ecosystems through equitable and sustainable management.
4. Pause harmful activities in the deep ocean while improving knowledge to enable sustainable and equitable uses.
5. Ensure equitable sharing of benefits derived from marine genetic resources.
6. End illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing and improve transparency.
7. Ensure sustainable, equitable, and safe ocean-based food systems.
8. Adopt comprehensive measures to end marine plastic pollution.
9. Decarbonize shipping and reduce the environmental impact of maritime transport.
10. Ensure ambitious investments in inclusive fundamental transdisciplinary knowledge generation to inform ocean action.

We also outline five cross-cutting recommendations to underpin these efforts:

Reinforce support to multilateral organizations to support fairness, inclusiveness, ecological safety, and precautionary principles.

Implement the already existing regulations and international commitments to protect the ocean and its vital services to society.

Eliminate subsidies that harm climate and biodiversity.

Strengthen oceanographic research, particularly by enhancing observation and modeling capacity and facilitating knowledge sharing.

Sustain and build on the momentum that will be generated by the Third United Nations Ocean Conference to strengthen the link between science and policy.

These recommendations serve as a framework for action, to ensure that science remains at the heart of efforts to secure a sustainable future for the ocean and humanity.

¹ The Ocean Action Panels of the Third United Nations Ocean Conference (UNOC) are thematic platforms designed to foster collaborative solutions and partnerships for achieving sustainable use and conservation of ocean resources, aligning with Sustainable Development Goal 14 (Life Below Water).